

Report on lessons learned and future prospects for adopting best practices

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Document Author(s):	Uwe Konrad (HZDR), Oliver Knodel (HZDR), Ana Valcarcel-Orti (SOLEIL), Antoine Padovani (SOLEIL), Clara Albert (SOLEIL), Marta Gutierrez (EGI)
Document Reviewer(s):	Sophie Servan; Paul Millar; Alun Ashton
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Abstract

Report on lessons learned and future prospects for adopting best practices in education and training (incl. the training platform) on data FAIR principles, data management and data stewardship at the ExPaNDS RIs and in the PaN community at large.

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Executive Summary

Training is an essential part of the ExPaNDS project. Education and training are increasingly important for helping scientists work on Photon and Neutron (PaN) sources. There is a strong need for training on FAIR principles, data governance, data management, catalogues, and data analysis services. Fragmentation in training resources is a challenge.

Activities of WP5 started at M12. ExPaNDS training activities have covered all the main results of the project: FAIR principles, metadata framework, catalogues, PaN ontology and solutions for data analysis. Training activities have been targeted towards both internal and external consortium audiences, RI staff and users. Due to the Covid-19 crisis, ExPaNDS had to rethink the way workshops were held. Workshops were done remotely or in a hybrid mode, allowing attendees to stay in their facilities for safety reasons (during lockdown periods) and were also useful to allow participants that would otherwise not join at all. Furthermore, these workshops were recorded, making them re-usable, and easily findable on the PaN-training platform.

ExPaNDS has also set up a supporting training framework under the form of a training activity plan (section 5, Annex 1) and a PaN-training platform (<https://pan-training.eu/>) developed in close collaboration with the PaNOSC project. Both the training plan and the platform have facilitated organisation and dissemination of training activities and promoted exchange of new knowledge. Notably, training workflows (<https://pan-training.eu/workflows>) are very useful to integrate different ExPaNDS training materials into coherent learning paths. The platform is registered as an EOSC service and is therefore part of the EOSC portal.

The contribution and support from all PaN community stakeholders here is key. The catalogue content has been so far provided by individual RIs or consortia in both ExPaNDS and PaNOSC, and is reaching out beyond our partners to other facilities (e.g. Stanford Synchrotron Radiation Lightsource) and groupings such as CERIC-ERIC, LEAPS, LENS and LaserLab Europe. Moreover, the training catalogue is based on an established solution developed by the ELIXIR community. This collaboration contributed to strengthen links between the ExPaNDS and the ELIXIR Community.

Finally, an analysis of future prospects has been performed to promote future collaborations with other projects in the PaN Community (e.g, DAPHNE4NFDI)

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Glossary

API: Application Programming Interface

ARIE: Analytical Research Infrastructures in Europe

DOI: Digital Object Identifier

ENVRI: Environmental Research Infrastructures

EOSC: European Open Science Cloud

ERIC: European Research Infrastructure Consortium

ExPaNDS: European Open Science Cloud Photon and Neutron Data Services

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

HPC: High Performance Computing

IEEE: Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

LEAPS: League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources

LENS: League of Advanced European Neutron Sources

LOM: Learning Object Metadata

PaN: Photon and Neutron

PaNET: Photon and Neutron Experimental Technique

PaNOSC: Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud

RIs: Research Infrastructures

VISA: Virtual Infrastructure for Scientific Analysis

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1. Introduction

Education and training are increasingly important for helping scientists work on Photon and Neutron (PaN) sources. The necessity for FAIR principles, data stewardship, data management, catalogues and data analysis services training exists. Fragmentation in learning and training resources (duplication, obsolete materials...) is also a challenge as it reduces their impact.

Training is an essential part of the **ExPaNDS** project. ExPaNDS partners aim to educate and train staff and users from PaN Research Infrastructures to exploit the services developed during the project by organizing a series of events and delivering training materials on a dedicated platform (Figure 1). Training **activities covered by WP5 started at M12**.

Figure 1. Summary of ExPaNDS WP5 goals and results

The **pan-training.eu** (<https://pan-training.eu/>) portal is a result of the two H2020 projects **ExPaNDS** and **PaNOSC**. The portal was officially released in August 2022. This portal consists firstly of a catalogue for the registration of PaN community related training events and training materials such as tutorials, videos, repositories, or training workflows to show learning steps and dependencies between materials. On the other hand, the portal also offers a tightly coupled e-learning system (Moodle) with PaN-specific learning courses with Jupyter notebook support.

Figure 2. ExPaNDS Training Catalogue registration at EOSC

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The PaN-Training catalogue has been registered as a dedicated service in the EOSC(<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/pan-training-catalogue>) enabling the training content to a wider user base beyond the PaN community (Figure 2).

The training catalogue is based on an established solution developed by the ELIXIR community. With the catalogue, ExPaNDS partners are strengthening the role of EOSC services for the PaN scientific field, with a focus on providing a sustainable training, learning and documentation platform for the PaN community including initiatives such as LEAPS, LENS, and Laserlab Europe.

The organization of several training events has also enabled the promotion and adoption of the outcomes of ExPaNDS. A number of workshops have been organized, covering a large range of services such as FAIR principles, data stewardship, data management, catalogues, and data analysis services developed during the project. These actions dedicated to facilities scientific software and computing staff, instrument scientists and users fostered faster adoption of best practices by an enlarged number of the PaN user community. All the materials and recordings of the workshops organized by ExPaNDS can be found in the training catalogue.

As of the end of January 2023, the platform gathers 185 materials including almost 50 courses gathered from the e-learning system (Moodle), as well as 312 events and 11 workflows.

The following sections depict the work performed by the ExPaNDS project to collect existing and support the creation of new training materials and contribute to ensure their diffusion, adoption, and re-use. The document also explores sustainability strategies and prospects.

2. Collection, preparation and publishing of training material

2.1. Collection of ExPaNDS related training material and training workflows

Fragmentation in learning and training resources is a challenge as it reduces their impact. Coordination, re-use and easy access to training materials is much needed.

The PaN-training.eu (<https://pan-training.eu/>) portal is a result of the two H2020 projects ExPaNDS and PaNOSC. A joint Task Force WP5 ExPaNDS and WP8 PaNOSC was created to facilitate the exchanges between these projects (monthly meetings). A demo version of the training portal was available in June 2021 (mid-term review). The final version was released in August 2022.

As of the end of January 2023, there are 185 materials, 312 events and 11 workflows in the training catalogue. Resources are either created manually or integrated in the platform via scrapers developed. Out of the 185 materials there are different types. The

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category "resource type" is used in the catalogue to distinguish them. The majority have been tagged as videos (80), then as slides (22), git/Git/github/Git project (15), document (14), tool (9) and jupyter notebook (6). There are also 48 materials (Moodle courses) from the e-learning platform. Most of the materials are provided with a DOI to increase their FAIRness.

Below is a pie chart (Figure 3) showing different resource types (only resource types present in 5 or more materials are counted). There is a slight difference in how resources are identified, see the difference between "slides", "video, slides" and "video" whereas in the count done above only "slides" and "video" are identified as resource types.

Figure 3. Training catalogue: Resource types (only resource types present in 5 or more materials are counted)

The materials in our catalogue are described by a metadata schema following the RDA metadata recommendations¹ with additional elements from the IEEE LOM² and the ENVRI³ training catalogues as described in our deliverable D5.4⁴. The classification of the materials is the responsibility of the submitting user or a curator of our community. In this context, **we integrated the PaNET ontology⁵ as optional field *scientific topic* in our metadata schema. The PaNET ontology developed in the framework of ExPaNDS was implemented in the training portal to describe training resources and make them accessible and easily searchable. Specifically, the user can find materials with a particular scientific topic and any of it's children. This can be done thanks to the PaNET ontology developed by WP3.**

The **content providers** for the materials include the PaNOSC (48 PaN Learning Moodle courses are available in the graph below) and the ExPaNDS projects (35 materials developed in the framework of the project) as well as external providers such as RIs and ERICs. External providers can use the platform to share their own materials. A third party

1 Recommendations for a minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00073>

2 IEEE Standard (IEEE 2002) for Learning Object Model (LOM)

3 ENVRI-FAIR MS22 Document: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3903340>

4 D5.4, Demonstrator for using e-learning platforms for PaN

5 <http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/>

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can also share materials indicating the content provider the material originates from. Among them, CERIC-ERIC, SOLEIL and ILL with 39, 15 and 8 materials available in the platform, respectively. Below is a pie chart (Figure 4) showing content providers with 5 or more materials uploaded. The catalogue also gathers materials from: Stanford SSRL, ALBA, ISIS, Diamond, HZDR, PSI, MAX IV, EU-XFEL and DESY.

Figure 4. Training catalogue content providers (with 5 or more materials uploaded)

ExPaNDS has developed **training content covering the main results of the project**. All findable ExPaNDS related **materials** that are relevant to the PaN community **have been uploaded to the catalogue**:

- WP2 produced materials related to FAIR data (workshops and guidelines). 13 materials were developed in the framework of this WP and are available via the platform: promotion of FAIR principles, data policy framework, data management ...
- In addition to all materials from WP3 (13), a workflow showcasing a “Learning path: Metadata catalogue services including PaN ontologies” has been created in the platform for a better integration of the different assets developed: data services, PaNET ontology, data catalogues ...
- Concerning materials on definition and reference data sets and data analysis services, workflows detailing the use cases developed in WP4⁶ have been created or are in progress.

In the second period of the project (M19 – M42), WP5 focused on developing training workflows with the technical WPs. Notably, **ExPaNDS WP5 in conjunction with WP4 worked on the development of training workflows** to better display the dependencies and connections between the different services and data pipelines involved in all the reference analysis services and its presence in EOSC, PaN data portal as well as RI’s dedicated catalogues. WP5 scheduled dedicated meetings with the analysis services owners to co-design the training workflows and deliver the corresponding entries in the PaN-training platform.

Some of the elements referenced in the workflow include:

- The experiment set up and technique involved in the data collection process.
- The reference datasets and DOIs with downloadable links.
- The analysis service utilised to process or analyse the data (including links to GitHub and further documentation).
- The outputs produced by the services (e.g. reduced data, reconstructed images...).

⁶ Deployment of analysis services for EOSC [10.5281/zenodo.7417726](https://zenodo.org/record/7417726)

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- The running environment (e.g. Jupyter Notebooks, containerised applications, workload managers to submit jobs to HPC environments, etc...).
- Any publications associated to the data or service if available.

Each of the nodes from the workflow represents an interactive entry with further resources available to that step of the workflow (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Example of one of the workflows available at the training platform.

The training workflows provide entry points and unified views of how all the ExPaNDS data and services can be combined for knowledge generation and support the scientists with the necessary steps to be able to reproduce existing baseline research.

Together with WP3, WP5 created a "learning path" on Metadata Catalogue services including PaN ontologies. The workflow gathers the workshop on delivering data services to EOSC (April 2021), a Hands-on session on the PaN ontologies API (February 2022), the Workshop on Metadata Catalogues (April 2022) and all related materials (<https://pan-training.eu/workflows/metadata-catalogue-services>).

SOLEIL has also launched a pilot experience to exploit workflows as guidelines for the facility users. Beamline staff at SOLEIL created a workflow that gathers all materials available (videos, guidelines, software ...) necessary to perform experiences at the beamline (from sample preparation and data acquisition to data analysis). The workflow is available in the training platform: <https://pan-training.eu/workflows/heliobio-soleil-disco-beamline>

The full list of materials (workshops, guidelines, GitHub content, Wikis, posters ...) developed in the framework of the ExPaNDS project **can be found in the project Training Activity plan in Annex 1 (section 5 of the present document)**. Dedicated footnotes allow the reader to directly access the targeted content in the platform.

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2.2. Workshops prepared and organized

The necessity for FAIR principles, data stewardship, data management, catalogues and data analysis services training exists. **ExPaNDS partners aim to educate and train staff and users from PaN Research Infrastructures to exploit the methods and services developed during the project** by organizing a series of events.

WP5 organised a series of **training events to support ExPaNDS objectives**. Events were organised **in close collaboration with the technical WPs (WP2, WP3 and WP4)**, who provided materials and defined the key needs, **and with WP6**, who took care of the organisational and promotional aspects. These training activities focused on the following topics: FAIR principles, EOSC services, metadata catalogues, PaNET ontology and VISA data analysis infrastructure. **PaNOSC partners were also involved** in the co-organisation or participated actively to these workshops.

Due to the Covid-19 crisis, ExPaNDS had to rethink the way workshops were held. This is the reason why **workshops were done remotely or in a hybrid mode**, allowing attendees to stay in their facilities for safety reasons (during lockdown periods) and were also useful to allow participants that would otherwise not join at all. Furthermore, these workshops were recorded, making them re-usable, and easily findable on the PaN-training platform (Figure 6).

The first **FAIR workshop** for ExPaNDS was held remotely on the 1st and 2nd October 2020. The second ExPaNDS workshop took place in April 2021 (**EOSC Workshop**, 6th and 7th April 2021). A hands-on session on the **PaN ontologies API** (Online, 17th February 2022) and a Workshop on **Metadata Catalogues** (Online, 4th April 2022) were organised and allowed us to create a dedicated learning path that gathers three workshops and all related materials (videos, guidelines, repositories). To continue the promotion of **main ExPaNDS WP3 results (catalogues, API, ontology...)**, an open session was organised (hybrid meeting, Saint Aubin, 3rd November 2022) as satellite of an internal ExPaNDS/PaNOSC meeting. A first **technical workshop** on the Virtual Infrastructure for Scientific Analysis (**VISA**) portal demonstration, set up and distribution was also organised (hybrid meeting - Dolní Břežany, 14th June 2022). This event was followed by a **second VISA workshop** that took place on 16th of September 2022 (Online). **Dedicated meetings** between the WP5 team and ExPaNDS facilities' staff have been organised to work on the **use of workflows**. The final workshop "**Follow a user story! A journey through the PaN data services**" took place in Hamburg on the 24th January 2023 (hybrid). The final workshop gathered 5 key presentations: **FAIR journey, EOSC demo, PaN-training platform demo, VISA portal and Search API/Harvesting presentations**. This workshop was organised as a satellite event of the Users' annual meeting at DESY/EuXFEL.

In addition, local events were held with users and staff at the various facilities, e.g., HZDR, and SOLEIL.

Figure 6. Screenshots of some of the workshop materials available in the ExPaNDS training catalogue

Technical KPIs	Value	Previous value
Number of attendees to the workshops (ExPaNDS / PaNOSC / other)	374/88/292 (01.2023)	284/61/157 (08.2022)
Number of users in the PaN training portal (ExPaNDS / PaNOSC / other)	127/125/750 (01.2023)	109/106/596 (08.2022)

The target set for the 5th objective of ExPaNDS, i.e. to raise the level of awareness and competence in FAIR data practices within user communities, was 500 participants in total to all ExPaNDS training workshops. This target was reached during the last year of the project.

3. Lessons learned, sustainability and the Future of PaN-training in the EOSC

3.1. ExPaNDS WP5 promotion activities

To promote the adoption of the ExPaNDS PaN-training platform and of the project developments, WP5 project partners have participated to diverse external events:

Event	WP5 participation	Audience targeted
Symposium for Librarians and data policy staff, 30th September 2021 (online)	Publishing the experiment (demonstration version of the platform), Oliver Knodel (HZDR)	Librarians and data policy staff
2nd European PaN EOSC Symposium 2021, 26th	TELBE Data Analysis workflow and the PaN	Staff of RIs

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October 2021 (online)	training platform UX, Jan-Christoph Deinert (HZDR)	
Workshop (in French): EOSC, a resource for research, 8th April 2022 (online)	Presentation of the PaN training platform (demo version), Ana Valcarcel Orti (SOLEIL)	Staff of RIs and users
LEAPS LENS Networks monthly IT staff meeting, 9th May 2022 (online)	Presentation of the PaN training platform (demo version), Uwe Konrad (HZDR)	IT staff of the facilities members of the LEAPs and LENS networks
LEAPS meets Quantum, 15th – 20th May 2022, in Elba	Poster, Oliver Knodel (HZDR)	Scientists at the RIs and Users from the Quantum community
ExPaNDS – PaNOSC meeting, hybrid-Prague, 14th – 15th June 2022	Presentation of the PaN training platform (demo version), Antoine Padovani (SOLEIL)	Members of the ExPaNDS and PaNOSC communities
ESUO General Assembly meeting, 29th – 30th August 2022 hybrid- Saint Aubin (SOLEIL's site)	Keynote, Majid OUNSY (SOLEIL) Special session dedicated to ExPaNDS results and how to access resources via the PaN training platform Poster	Users of RIs
EGI meeting, 20th – 22nd September 2022 in Prague	Poster	RIs staff and users. Stakeholders
LEAPS Annual Plenary, 26th – 28th October 2022 in Villigen (PSI premises)	Poster	Staff members RIs in the LEAPS network. Representatives of the EC
EOSC Symposium 2022, 14th – 17th November 2022 in Prague	Flash presentation, Oliver Knodel (HZDR)	EOSC community
DAPHNE4NFDI work meeting 2022, 5th – 7th December 2022 in Hamburg	Presentation, Oliver Knodel (HZDR)	DAPHNE4NFDI partners
SOLEIL's users meeting, 19th – 20th January 2023 in Saint Aubin (SOLEIL's site)	Poster Ana Valcarcel Orti (SOLEIL) panellist at the round table "Data analysis management"	Users of RIs

A video and a presentation are also available on the PaN-training platform under <https://pan-training.eu/about> and <https://pan-training.eu/about/us#publications> as well as a workflow explaining how to add training content <https://pan-training.eu/workflows/workflow-for-adding-content>.

WP5 also actively collaborates with WP6. WP5 prepared a promotional video presenting the PaN-training platform and its content. This video will be used by WP6 in a series of six topic-based webinars, which will involve a keynote speaker from a science technique or discipline who will deliver a talk and give us the opportunity to showcase some of the outcomes of the ExPaNDS project.

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3.2. ExPaNDS WP5 follow up on the impact of promotion activities

A demo version of the training catalogue was available in June 2021 (mid-term review). **The final version was only released in August 2022** (<https://pan-training.eu/>).

Below is a graph showing the monthly visits to the PaN-training platform (Figure 7). **This data was collected with our analytics system. This system is GDPR compliant.**

Figure 7. Graph showing the monthly visits to the PaN-training platform

To corroborate this data, here are two graphs coming from data from the google search console, showing impressions and clicks over time (Figure 8 and 9).

Figure 8. Graph showing the monthly impressions to the PaN-training platform

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Figure 9. Graph showing the monthly clicks to the PaN-training platform

Both **impressions and clicks are increasing**, confirming the upward trends from our own analytics.

Concerning signups to the training platform, getting an upward trend of users continuously signing up is an objective to strive for.

Regarding **backlinks** here are a few sites that link to the PaN-training platform: panosc.eu, eli-laser.eu, zenodo.org, [github \(io and com\)](https://github.com), egi.eu, dragon.lv, esuo.eu, eoscfuture.eu, elixir-europe.org, cells.es, fairdataforum.org, dataacc.org, rd-alliance.org.

As indicated in subsection 3.1, the PaN-training platform was presented at various events (e.g. EGI Conference 2022, EOSC Symposium 2022) and **possible joint developments were discussed with ELIXIR and representatives of the EOSC**. Especially, a joint development on uniform access to blended learning courses could be something that ELIXIR is also interested in. Moreover, a small contribution was made to the ELIXIR code base by WP5 members. **As a direct result of the EOSC Symposium 2022, we moved forward with the final registration of PaN-training as a service within the EOSC marketplace.**

3.3. ExPaNDS WP5 sustainability actions

In the **sustainability** session of the ExPaNDS Closing Event in January 2023 the sustainability sheets of PaN EOSC outcomes were discussed with the objective of maximising the sustainability of the results of the ExPaNDS project. **The PaN-training catalogue was identified as a significant outcome that must be preserved in the long term.** In terms of sustainability a distinction between the provision of hardware resources for computing and storage and the corresponding maintenance of the service, as well as the curation of the materials is unavoidable. **Regarding the hardware resources, the HZDR has agreed to provide infrastructure and the service in the long term.** Here, the maintenance can also be handled by the HIFIS group within HZDR. In addition, the training

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catalogue can be extended and used as an overarching training portal within the Helmholtz association for additional communities beyond the PaN community. First steps in this direction have already been taken.

In terms of curation, we are working to mobilise the community, e.g. LENS, LEAPS and Laserlab Europe, as well as the RIs listed in our content provider section of [PaN-training.eu](https://pan-training.eu). From within the Helmholtz Association, more specifically the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration⁷, we started a discussion to hand over the curation. Here, it is important to mention that the additional projects are also interested to adapt and develop the platform for further use (e.g. [DAPHNE4NFDI](https://daphne4nfdi.eu)). Especially, the further developments of the platform are possible, due to the fact that our codebase is completely open source and a contribution policy is in place⁸.

3.4. Summary of lessons learned and future prospects for adopting best practices

Lessons learned are depicted in the previous sections and are **summarized here**:

- Much of the project took place under pandemic conditions, so the interactive trainings and workshops in particular had to be redesigned. Users from all sides could attend from home offices without travel restrictions. In addition, training events could easily be recorded. But also, for the workflows of the experiments addressed in this project, new challenges but also opportunities arose. These workflows make it easier to understand the remote procedures (concerning remote computing access, sample handling ...) put into place.
- Feedback from attendees to online/hybrid workshops: Attendees stressed that the online sessions made it easier for them to attend. They also pointed out that the online format was suitable to present the new results developed during the project. However, they indicated that the duration should be kept reasonable (or introduce virtual coffee breaks) and a stronger involvement of the moderator is needed to insure the interactions with the remote attendees. Presentations encouraged them to follow future developments.
- The evaluation of the Moodle platform (developed by PaNOSC) showed that it is not suitable as a single point of information and training for all types of assets. Fragmentation of resources and overload of information results in a lack of knowledge. Therefore, and to avoid duplication of resources, a common training portal (<https://pan-training.eu/>) was developed based on the training platform of the European bioinformatics project ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/training>), which includes the above mentioned Moodle platform and a new training catalogue that allows the storage of all assets. The PaN-Training platform has been also

⁷ <https://helmholtz-metadaten.de/en>

⁸ PaN-training contribution policy on [GitHub](https://github.com).

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registered as a dedicated service in the EOSC enabling the training content to a wider user base beyond the PaN community

- The first prototype of the training catalogue was released and presented (live demonstration) during the mid-term review meeting in June 2021 (more than one year before the official release date). In retrospect, it was the right decision to open the catalogue to the public as early as possible, because this enabled us to motivate our scientist to evaluate the platform and register first content early on in the project. With the planned release date more than one year later, the number of materials and the overall adoption of the platform would be significantly lower.
- Regular exchanges between members of WP5 and other project partners took place throughout the project. These exchanges were key to identify the content to be uploaded to the platform and create the training workflows. Involvement of staff members in charge of training activities at the facilities should be promoted.

The valuable **recommendations during the mid-term Review meeting** (June 2021) have been carefully reviewed and fully implemented within the development of the PaN-training platform:

- This development was realized together with the PANOSC project, the organizations EGI, LEAPS, LENS as well as (as already mentioned) with ELIXIR. The content was contributed by these partners or is linked automatically (like the events in the calendar) into this portal. In addition, the platform is registered as an EOSC service, and it is therefore part of the EOSC portal. Finally, the technical basis is being further developed together with ELIXIR based on open source.
- ExPaNDS has developed training content covering the main results of the project (workshops, guidelines, Wiki, GitHub content and videos): FAIR principles, data governance, data management, catalogues, API, ontologies, data analysis services and the use of the training platform.
- To exploit the potential of the platform to host and manage integrated assets, WP5 focused on developing training workflows with the technical WPs in the second period of the project (M19-42). The training workflows provide entry points and unified views of how all the ExPaNDS data and services can be combined for knowledge generation and support the scientists with the necessary steps to be able to reproduce existing baseline research.

WP5 ExPaNDS partners have also explored potential prospects and identified ongoing European projects candidates for future collaborations. In particular, the DAPHNE4NFDI project and the Helmholtz Association are very interested in using and developing our platform, still under the name PaN-training.eu. The list of European project candidates is available in the Annex 2 (section 6 of the present document).

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4. Conclusion

There is a great need for training on FAIR principles, data governance, data management, catalogues, and data analysis services. Through dedicated training events ExPaNDS has reached a significant number of members of the PaN community. Due to the Covid-19 crisis, workshops have been thus organised online or in a hybrid mode. These webinars have been recorded, making them easily re-usable.

Looking closer at the trainings themselves, they covered all main results of the ExPaNDS project: FAIR principles, metadata framework, catalogues on PaN ontology and solutions for data analysis.. Training activities have been targeted towards both internal and external consortium audiences, RI staff and users. The participation of ExPaNDS partners to the ESUO (European Synchrotron and Free Electron Laser User Organisation) General Assembly meeting and to the SOLEIL's users meeting contributed to reach the RIs users' community. The organisation of the final workshop as a satellite event of the DESY/EuXFEL Annual Users' meeting contributed to this objective, too.

ExPaNDS has also set up a supporting training framework under the form of a training activity plan (section 5, Annex 1) and a PaN-training platform (<https://pan-training.eu/>) developed in close collaboration with the PaNOSC project. Both the training plan and the platform have facilitated the organisation and dissemination of training activities and promoted the exchange of new knowledge. Moreover, the metadata of the training materials in the training catalogue can either be reused or integrated in similar external applications to spread the content widely using third party portals.

A major challenge is the question of keeping gathered information up to date. The contribution and support from all PaN community stakeholders here is key. The catalogue content has been contributed by RIs groupings such as LEAPS, LENS, LaserLab Europe, or CERIC-ERIC and consortia (e.g. H2020 LEAPS-INNOV) or is linked automatically into the training portal. ExPaNDS partners have also actively participated in external events to promote the training activities, among them, the 2nd European PaN EOSC Symposium 2021, the workshop EOSC a resource for research and the EOSC Symposium 2022. In addition, the platform is registered as an EOSC service and is therefore part of the EOSC portal.

Moreover, the training platform is based on an established solution developed by the ELIXIR community. This collaboration contributed to strengthen links between the LEAPS, LENS and the ELIXIR Communities.

Finally, an analysis of future prospects has been performed to promote future collaborations with other projects in the PaN Community (e.g. DAPHNE4NFDI, eRIImote, ReMade@ARI)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857641.

5. Annex 1: ExPaNDS full training activity plan

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
WP1 T5.1.2	Workshop (online)	Develop common rules and best practices between national RIs and harmonise the provision of the EOSC services ⁹	IT staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs ¹⁰ facility scientist and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M12	Done - 6 th - 7 th Apr. 2021
WP2 T2.4/ T2.6/ T5.3	Workshop series (online)	Workshop 1: Best Practice Sharing Meeting - DOIs/PIDs for Datasets - Policy and Implementation Workshop 2: Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for Facility Research ¹¹	ExPaNDS / PaNOSC RIs	M17/M26	Both workshops were completed. First workshop 28 th January 2021, organised by WP2 with additional content provided by WP3 and PaNOSC. Second workshop 22 nd October 2021, organised by WP2 with additional content provided by JLSRF (Jülich), B2INST (GWDG), HMC Matter (HZB), and DataCite
WP2 T2.4/ T2.6	Guidelines	Advanced infrastructure for PIDs in PaN RIs ¹²	Facility scientist and staff of ESFRI and national PaN	M31	Completed - March 2022

⁹ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/develop-common-rules-and-best-practices-between-national-ri-s-and-harmonize-the-provision-of-the-eosc-services>

¹⁰ Stakeholders "ESFRI and national PaN RIs" include LEAPS, LENS and CERIC, ELI...

¹¹ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/persistent-identifiers-for-facilities-research-workshop>

¹² <https://pan-training.eu/materials/advanced-infrastructure-for-pids-in-photon-and-neutron-ris>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
			RIs		
WP2 T2.1	Guidelines	Data Policy Framework First draft released at M12. Final version released at M24 ¹³	Facility scientist and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M12 - M24 - M30	Completed - September 2021
WP2 T2.1/ T2.6/ T5.3	Guidance Note	Guidance note related to Draft Data Policy Framework Revised Guidance note related to Final Version Data Policy Framework ¹⁴	Facility scientist and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M18/M30	Draft version completed - January 2020 Final version completed - February 2022
WP2 T2.6/ T5.1.1	Workshop Series (online)	Promote FAIR principles ¹⁵ Workshop 1: FAIR for Facilities ¹⁶ Workshop 2: The FAIR Experiment ¹⁷	Facility scientists and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M12	Done - 1 st - 2 nd Oct. 2020 Videos available via the training catalogue
WP2 T2.6/	Seminar (online)	Symposium for Librarians and Data Managers ¹⁸	PaN librarians and data managers	M25	Done - 30 th September 2021

¹³ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/expands-d2-3-final-data-policy-framework-for-photon-and-neutron-ris>

¹⁴ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/expands-guidance-note-key-policy-elements-within-a-photon-and-neutron-research-infrastructure-data-policy-framework-revised-final-version>

¹⁵ <https://pan-training.eu/events/expands-fair-workshop>

¹⁶ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/fair-for-facilities>

¹⁷ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/the-fair-experiment>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
T5.3					
WP2 T2.6/ T5.3	Presentation (online - external speakers)	Assessing the FAIRness of a prototypical PaN instrument at BESSY II ¹⁹	Facility scientists and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M27	Done - 15 th November 2021 Video available via the training catalogue
WP2 T2.3/ T2.6/ T5.3	Workshop (online)	Workshop to present and get feedback on the metadata framework and its implementation at PaN instruments ²⁰ (Related to metadata framework)	Facility scientists and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M31	Done - 2 nd March 2022 Video available via the training catalogue
WP2 T2.3/ T5.3	Guidelines	Metadata framework and recommendations for FAIR PaN data management First draft released at M16 ²¹	Facility scientists and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M16 - M34	First deliverable completed - 14 th December 2020 Second deliverable published - July 2022 ²²
WP2	Guidelines	Data Management Plans	Facility scientists	M27/M39	First deliverable: published November

18 <https://pan-training.eu/events/expands-symposium-for-librarians-and-data-managers>

19 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/beamline-fairness-assessment-presentation>

20 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/fair-metadata-workshop>

21 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/draft-recommendations-for-fair-photon-and-neutron-data-management>

22 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/final-recommendations-for-fair-photon-and-neutron-data-management>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
T2.2/ T5.3		for PaN RIs First deliverable on DMPs for PaN RIs ²³ Second deliverable: Active DMPs for PaN RIs ²⁴	and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs		2021 Second deliverable published Dec 2022
WP2 T2.5/ T2.6	Guidelines	Self-evaluation Photon and Neutron RIs for FAIR data certification ²⁵	Facility scientists and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M39	Completed – published Dec 2022
WP2 T2.5/ T2.6	Workshop series (online)	Promote and discuss FAIR self-assessment exercise Workshop 1: Presentation of the FAIR self-assessment questions and report template . Note that this workshop will not be recorded. Workshop 2: Reporting of outcomes from FAIR self-	Facility scientists and staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M35/M37	Completed. First workshop: 6 Jul 2022 Second workshop: 26 Sep 2022

²³ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/rdmo-research-data-management-organiser>

²⁴ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/active-dmps-for-photon-and-neutron-ris#home>

²⁵ <https://pan-training.eu/materials/self-evaluation-photon-and-neutron-ris-for-fair-data-certification#home>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
		assessment. Workshop not to be recorded.			
WP3 T5.3	Wiki. Linked to Workshop Develop common rules and best practices between national RI's and harmonise the provision of the EOSC services	Delivering data services to EOSC: OAI-PMH, metadata, harvesting, SciCat, ICAT, B2FIND, OpenAIRE, research data ²⁶	Open to ESFRI and national PaN RIs via the training platform	M20	Done - April 2021
WP3 T5.3	WIKI GitHub Document	ExPaNDS NexusOntology ²⁷ It is expected that this ontology will be maintained by the Nexus International Advisory Committee (NIAC)	IT and facility scientist of ESFRI and national PaN RIs + NIAC	M21	Done Published on the training platform NeXus ontology and mapping dcat ontology and nexus
WP3 T5.3	Document GitHub	PaNET ontology ²⁸	IT and facility scientist of ESFRI and national PaN	M31	Completed

26 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/delivering-data-services-to-eosc>

27 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/expands-nexusontology-machine-readable-ontology-of-the-nexus-definitions>
<https://pan-training.eu/materials/expands-mapping-dcat-ontology-and-nexus>
<https://pan-training.eu/materials/expands-d3-2-ontologies>

28 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/expands-photon-and-neutron-experimental-techniques-panet-ontology>
<https://pan-training.eu/materials/pan-ontologies-api>
<https://pan-training.eu/materials/expands-d3-2-ontologies>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
			RIs		
WP3 T5.3	Document and GitHub	Metadata Catalogue Release ²⁹ : how a self-contained, stand-alone metadata catalogue release was developed for facilities to test and try locally	IT and facility scientist of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M24	Done - August 2021
WP3 T5.3	Guidelines for users (User guide, targeted examples for PaN community, tutorials...)	EOSC data catalogue services: SciCat/ICAT document and provide technical information on systems, APIs and user interfaces ³⁰	IT of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M31 - M34	Completed
WP3 T5.1.4	Workshop (online): Presentation of the User Guidelines for PaN <i>Learning path</i>	Educate and train IT staff and scientists on the metadata catalogue services ³¹	IT of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M32	Done - 4 April 2022

29 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/metadata-catalogue-release>

30 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/common-search-api-definition>

<https://pan-training.eu/materials/report-on-status-gap-analysis-and-roadmap-towards-harmonised-and-federated-metadata-catalogues-for-eu-national-photon-and-neutron-ris>

<https://pan-training.eu/materials/demonstrate-icat-and-scat-released-with-apis-compatible-with-expands-federated-eosc-services>

<https://pan-training.eu/materials/scicat-ingestion-approaches>

31 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/workshop-on-metadata-catalogues>

<https://pan-training.eu/workflows/metadata-catalogue-services>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
	<i>associated (workflow)</i>				
WP3 T5.3	Workshop (hybrid) Joint Public Session ExPaNDS/PaNOSC on metadata catalogues (SciCat implementation) and future perspectives	Promote PIDs: options for persistent identifiers for raw data and the metadata to be registered along with those identifiers ³²	IT and facility staff of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M39	Done – 3 rd November 2022 Saint-Aubin (SOLEIL's site)
WP4 T5.1.5	First Workshop on the Virtual Infrastructure for Scientific Analysis (hybrid)	VISA portal demo, set up and distribution	IT staff of PaNOSC and ExPaNDS projects	M34	Done - 14 June 2022 online - Prague
WP4 T5.1.5	VISA workshop (online)	Educate and train PaN users in the use of the data analysis services ³³	IT, facility staff and end user of ESFRI and national PaN RIs	M37	Done - 16 th September 2022
WP3/ WP4 T5.1.3	Training session (online)	Educate and train developers and facility staff on how to deploy and support their own	IT and facility staff of ExPaNDS partners	M34 – M40	Done, dedicated meetings between WP5 and the facilities staff

32 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/work-package-3-public-meeting>

33 <https://pan-training.eu/materials/virtual-infrastructure-for-scientific-analysis-visa-workshop>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
		workflows ³⁴			
WP5/All WPs	Workshop	Keynote presentation + Poster ³⁵	Users ESUO and ENSA Networks	M36	Done, 29 th - 30 th August in Saint Aubin (SOLEIL's site)
All WPs	Final event Workshop (hybrid)	User's Journey The objective was to demonstrate how as a user, one can benefit from the services developed during the project. ³⁶	Users IT and Facility scientist of ESFRI and national PaN RIs,	M41	Done, 24 th January 2023 Hamburg (DESY premises, Annual DESY users' meeting)
WP5 T5.2/ T5.3	Promotion activities Series of seminars + poster + video demonstrating the catalogue	How to customise and use the training catalogue: Register new external materials (available on Zenodo, GitHub, websites), introduce (not execute) workflows and promote events	IT and Facility scientist of ESFRI and national PaN RIs, Users and stakeholders	M25 – M42	Done - Seminars that took place up to date: Symposium for Librarians and data policy staff 30 th September 2021 Publishing the experiment Oliver Knodel (HZDR) 2nd European PaN EOSC Symposium 2021 26 th October 2021 TELBE Data Analysis workflow and the PaN training platform UX Jan-Christoph Deinert (HZDR)

34 <https://pan-training.eu/workflows>

35 <https://www.esuo.eu/18th-and-2022-annual-meeting-of-the-european-synchrotron-and-fel-user-organisation/>

36 <https://pan-training.eu/zenodomaterials/expands-workshop-follow-a-user-story-a-journey-through-the-pan-data-services>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
					<p>Workshop (in French): EOSC, a resource for research 8th April 2022 Ana Valcarcel Orti (SOLEIL)</p> <p>LEAPS LENS Networks monthly IT staff meeting 9th May 2022 Poster Uwe Konrad (HZDR)</p> <p>LEAPS meets Quantum 15th - 20th May 2022 in Elba Poster Oliver Knodel (HZDR)</p> <p>ExPaNDS – PaNOSC meeting hybrid Prague 14th - 15th June 2022 Antoine Padovani (SOLEIL)</p> <p>ESUO General Assembly meeting 29th - 30th August in Saint Aubin (SOLEIL's site) Poster</p> <p>EGI meeting Poster 20th - 22nd September 2022 in Prague Poster Marta Gutierrez (EGI)</p>

WP Task	Type of training	Topic	Targeted audience/ stakeholders	Date	Status
					<p>LEAPS Annual Plenary 26th – 28th October 2022 Villigen (PSI premises) Poster</p> <p>EOSC Symposium 2022 14th – 17th November 2022 Prague Flash presentation Oliver Knodel (HZDR)</p> <p>DAPHNE4NFDI work meeting 2022, 5th – 7th December 2022 in Hamburg Presentation, Oliver Knodel (HZDR)</p> <p>SOLEIL's users meeting 19th-20th January 2023 Saint Aubin (SOLEIL's site) Poster</p> <p>A video is also available on the training platform³⁷ as well as a workflow explaining how to add training content³⁸</p>

37 <https://pan-training.eu/about>

38 <https://pan-training.eu/workflows/workflow-for-adding-content>

6. Annex 2: List of project prospects

EOSC Future

[EOSC Future EOSC Future - EOSC Future](#)

The EU-funded EOSC Future project will integrate, consolidate and connect e-infrastructures, research communities and initiatives in Open Science to advance the EOSC platform of services (EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange, Interoperability Framework). The project aims to uncover the potential of European research by connecting the major stakeholders in the EOSC ecosystem, developing scientific use cases in collaboration with the thematic communities, engaging the broader EOSC community and increasing its visibility.

The PaN-training catalogue (<https://pan-training.eu/>) is registered a productive service within the EOSC marketplace³⁹.

eRIMote - Enhancing Remote Access to Research Infrastructures

[Home Page \(erimote.eu\)](#)

The eRImote project is the first to consider solutions for digital and remote service provision across RI domains and to look for transferable practices and new developments that will improve accessibility and resilience of RI infrastructures.

While existing processes will be collected, eRImote will also explore new solutions using defined use cases to develop and test their implementation in RI scenarios. This will take us beyond the state-of-the-art for concrete solutions. The eRImote consortium is relatively small with eight beneficiary participants representing four main ESFRI RI Roadmap domains. However, the consortium extends much more broadly through the existing contacts and networking partners of each of the project participants, increasing the reach out to hundreds of individuals, other European and global RIs, scientific networks, RI users, industry partners and policy makers.

DAPHNE4NFDI - Data for PHoton and Neutron Experiments and is a project funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) for a National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

[DAPHNE - Startseite \(daphne4nfdi.de\)](#)

DAPHNE4NFDI focuses on research with photons and neutrons at large-scale research facilities. The main goal of DAPHNE is to make data from photon and neutron experiments "FAIR", thereby making scientific work more efficient and gaining more knowledge from the data. The consortium thus aims at a national research data infrastructure along a process chain from the proposal, the experiment, data recorded, stored, analyzed and interpreted.

In The DAPHNE project training has a significant role and the further use of the PaN-training catalogue (<https://pan-training.eu/>) is currently under discussion. The project may involve further development, new materials or courses.

I.FAST – Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

[Home | IFAST \(ifast-project.eu\)](#)

³⁹ The PaN-Training Catalogue service within the EOSC marketplace: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/pan-training-catalogue>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857641.

I.FAST aims to enhance innovation in the particle accelerator community, mapping out and facilitating the development of breakthrough technologies common to multiple accelerator platforms. The project involves 49 partners, including 17 companies as co-innovation partners, to explore new alternative accelerator concepts and advanced prototyping of key technologies. These include, among others, new accelerator designs and concepts, advanced superconducting technologies for magnets and cavities, techniques to increase brightness of synchrotron light sources, strategies and technology to improve energy efficiency, and new societal applications of accelerators.

LEAPS-INNOV – LEAPS pilot to foster open innovation for accelerator-based light sources in Europe

[Home | LEAPS-INNOV - Open innovation](#)

The LEAPS-INNOV pilot project focusses on the implementation of new strategies and activities for long-term partnerships between industry and the European light sources, synchrotrons, and free-electron lasers, with their tens of thousands of users. LEAPS-INNOV aims at kick-starting the implementation of the LEAPS Technology Roadmap and, at the same time, at fostering a partnership with European industry through open innovation. It will offer joint technological developments and advanced research capabilities with LEAPS members for industry as collaborator, supplier, and user.

In the context of LEAPS the long-term use of the PaN-training catalogue (<https://pan-training.eu/>) is under discussion. This is not about providing or maintaining the catalog, but primarily about curating and creating events, materials, courses or workflows.

Remade@ARI – Recyclable materials development at analytical research infrastructures

[ReMade@ARI | This is the website of the EU financed project ReMade@ARI \(remade-project.eu\)](#)

In ReMade@ARI, the most significant European analytical research infrastructures join forces to pioneer a support hub for materials research facilitating a step change to the Circular Economy. ReMade@ARI offers coordinated access to more than 50 European analytical research infrastructures, comprising most of the facilities that constitute the Analytical Research Infrastructures in Europe (ARIE) network. ReMade@ARI offers comprehensive services suiting any research focusing on the development of new materials for the Circular Economy in the key areas highlighted in the CEAP and plays an important role in the preparation of the common technology roadmap for circular industries.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857641.